

Synthesis of Potential Pesticidal Agents : Thioureas Derived from Heterocyclic Amines

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2-Amino-5-substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been condensed with different aryl isothiocyanates under different reaction conditions to give eighteen 1,3-disubstituted unsymmetrical thioureas. The structures have been confirmed by spectral studies.

THE fungicidal action of sulphur containing compounds are well known. Various thiourea derivatives have been successfully screened as antibacterial¹, antifungal^{2,3}, antitubercular and antineoplastic^{4,5} agents. Oxadiazoles and their derivatives themselves are well known chemotherapeutic agents and their utility as antifungal^{6,7}, hypoglycemic⁸, carcinostatic⁹, diuretic¹⁰, antiviral¹¹ and bactereostatic¹² agents is already reported. These facts led us to synthesize a number of thioureas derived from various 2-amino-5-substituted oxadiazoles in the hope of getting compounds of enhanced pesticidal value.

The 2-amino-5-substituted 1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles were prepared by the methods reported in literature¹³. They were converted into their corresponding thiourea derivatives by reacting with different arylisothiocyanates¹⁴.

The infrared spectra of thioureas showed a sharp and strong band at 3390 cm⁻¹ (aryl-NH stretching) and

a broad band around 3200 cm⁻¹ (-NH stretching of the second -NH group). Characteristic bands of the benzene ring near 1600 and 1500 cm⁻¹ and bands in the range of 1545 cm⁻¹ and 1255 cm⁻¹ are due to >C=S stretching¹⁵. The bands in the region 1669-1650 cm⁻¹ are due to C=N stretching of the oxadiazoles nucleus. Sharp peaks in the region 3050-3000 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of C-H stretching vibration and variable peaks in the range 780-750 cm⁻¹ are due to -CH bending vibrations of aromatic rings.

Experimental

All the m.ps. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

2-Amino-5 phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole : It was prepared from benzaldehyde semicarbazone according to the method reported by Scott et al.¹³ m.p. 245°d. (reported 241-243°d.) other new 2-amino-5-substituted 1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles were prepared similarly and are reported in Table 1 alongwith their relevant data.

TABLE 1

2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

S.N.	R	Molecular Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Analysis %		
					C	H	N
1.	Phenyl	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ O	80	248 dec.	f 60.1 c 59.6	4.4 4.3	26.1 26.0
2.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	67	248	f 55.9 c 56.5	5.1 4.7	20.8 21.9
3.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O	75	205	f 58.9 c 58.8	6.1 5.8	21.4 22.5
4.	Cinnamal	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ O	80	185	f 64.9 c 64.1	5.1 4.8	21.3 22.4
5.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-phenyl	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	63	205	f 52.0 c 52.1	4.6 4.3	20.2 20.2
6.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₈ H ₇ N ₃ O ₂	72	285	f 54.4 c 54.2	4.2 3.7	24.1 23.7

f = Found values ; c = Calculated values

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TABLE 2

S.N.	R	R'	Molecular Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Analysis %		
						C	H	N
1.	<i>p</i> -anisyl	Phenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	65	185	f 57.8 c 58.8	5.0 4.2	17.2 17.1
2.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino phenyl	-do-	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₆ OS	72	182	f 60.4 c 60.1	5.1 5.0	20.7 20.6
3.	Cinnamal	-do-	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS	53	215	f 63.8 c 63.3	4.5 4.3	18.5 17.3
4.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	-do-	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	59	130	f 56.3 c 56.1	4.1 4.0	15.2 16.3
5.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	-do-	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	70	230	f 58.1 c 57.6	4.2 3.8	18.1 17.9
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	<i>o</i> -Phenetyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	75	205	f 58.6 c 58.3	4.8 4.8	15.6 15.1
7.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-phenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₆ OS	60	225	f 61.2 c 61.1	5.4 5.3	19.6 19.8
8.	Cinnamal	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ ClOS	63	220	f 57.6 c 57.2	3.6 3.6	16.1 15.7
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	68	190	f 59.6 c 60.0	4.5 4.6	16.6 16.4
10.	-do-	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	70	230 dec.	f 58.6 c 60.0	4.6 4.6	16.5 16.4
11.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	68	230 dec.	f 56.9 c 57.3	4.5 4.4	16.1 15.7
12.	-do-	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	59	185	f 57.2 c 57.3	4.6 4.4	16.2 15.7
13.	-do-	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	60	235 dec.	f 57.8 c 57.3	4.6 4.4	16.4 15.7
14.	Salicylal	-do-	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	63	220	f 59.2 c 58.8	4.3 4.2	17.2 17.1
15.	Cinnamal	-do-	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS	75	225 dec.	f 64.6 c 64.2	4.8 4.7	17.1 16.6
16.	Phenyl	-do-	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS	60	180	f 62.1 c 61.9	4.6 4.5	18.1 18.0
17.	<i>p</i> -Dimethyl-aminophenyl	-do-	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₆ OS	50	220 dec.	f 62.2 c 61.1	5.8 5.3	20.1 19.8

f = Found values, c = Calculated values.

1-(5-phenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2 yl)-3-phenyl thiourea : 2-Amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole 1.5 g. (0.009 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) by heating and added to an alcoholic solution of phenylisothiocyanate (1.2 g ; 0.008 mole dissolved in 8 ml of alcohol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2.5 hr. on cooling, a crystalline precipitate was obtained which was filtered and washed several times with ethanol and finally crystallised with alcohol. Yield 70%, m.p. 190° (Found C, 60.0 ; H, 4.95 ; N, 19.1. C₁₆H₁₂N₄OS requires C, 60.8 ; H, 4.5 ; N, 18.9%)

Other thioureas were prepared similarly and are presented in Table 2 alongwith relevant physical data.

All the thioureas are being evaluated for their pesticidal activities and the results will be communicated in a separate paper.

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